

ISSN 1391-0256

Journal of the Sri Lanka Association for the Advancement of Science

Volume 5 Issue 1 2023

JSLAAS

Founded in 1944 and incorporated by the Act of Parliament No 11 of 1966.

Journal of the Sri Lanka Association for the Advancement of Science is a biannual publication. Selected research work from annual research sessions (based on scientific merit) as well as other research articles are invited to submit research manuscripts as per the guidelines provided by SLAAS. SLAAS members may also separately submit their papers for publication.

The Journal can be accessed on-line to view and download the full text of the articles published respective to the volumes free of charge

Submission Manuscript

Only online submission, Web: <https://journal.slaas.lk>, *e-ISSN: 2682-6992*

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